

Comparison of Pain Outcomes Following Preservation versus Elective Division of the Ilioinguinal Nerve in Lichtenstein Mesh Repair

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Abstract:

Background: Chronic groin pain following hernia repair is a significant complication after inguinal hernia surgery. To mitigate this issue, some suggest routinely excising the ilioinguinal nerve. This study aimed to compare the outcomes of routine ilioinguinal nerve excision versus nerve preservation on chronic groin pain and other sensory symptoms following Lichtenstein inguinal hernia repair.

Methods: This research was carried out at the Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College, over 12 months from March 2023 to March 2024. Sixty patients with uncomplicated inguinal hernia who met the study criteria and were scheduled for Lichtenstein hernioplasty were randomly assigned to two groups: 30 patients underwent ilioinguinal nerve preservation (Group A), and 30 patients had elective nerve excision (Group B). Patients were followed for up to one year, with assessments focusing on pain, hypoesthesia, and numbness. Data were compared and analysed.

Results: At one year, the incidence of post-operative neuralgia was 23.33% in Group A and 6.67% in Group B ($p=0.05$), indicating a significant difference in pain outcomes between the two groups. However, the incidence of post-operative hypoesthesia was 10% in Group A versus 16.67% in Group B ($p>0.05$), and the incidence of numbness was 11.11% in Group A versus 16.67% in Group B ($p>0.05$), with no statistically significant difference between the groups for these symptoms.

Conclusions: Elective excision of the ilioinguinal nerve during Lichtenstein hernia repair significantly reduces the incidence of chronic groin pain post-surgery.

Keywords: Chronic groin pain, Inguinal hernia, Ilioinguinal nerve, Lichtenstein repair.

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Introduction

Chronic groin pain is a prevalent issue following open inguinal hernia repair, with reported rates ranging from 18% to 61.9% [1-3]. Even mild pain can significantly impact quality of life, interfering with daily activities [4-5], and in severe cases, the condition can be debilitating and challenging to manage. The ilioinguinal nerve, that supplies sensation to the groin, medial thigh, upper scrotum & penile root, is often seen in open hernia repairs.

Historically, surgical practice has favoured preserving this nerve to avoid sensory deficits and chronic pain. Nevertheless, recent reports have suggested that elective excision of the ilioinguinal nerve results in minimal morbidity and is generally well tolerated by patients [6,7]. Furthermore, ilioinguinal neurectomy has been shown to effectively alleviate chronic groin pain compared to

nerve block or mesh removal alone [8-10]. Recent retrospective studies also indicate that nerve excision during hernia repair is associated with reduced chronic pain postoperatively [11-12].

This trial investigates the impact of prophylactic ilioinguinal neurectomy on the frequency and severity of chronic groin pain after inguinal hernia repair using Lichtenstein's mesh technique, conducted in a prospective randomized controlled fashion.

Methods and Materials:

This study involved 50 male patients aged 18 to 60 years undergoing unilateral inguinal hernia repair using Lichtenstein's polypropylene mesh at Mahatma Gandhi Hospital. Participants were randomly assigned to receive either prophylactic

ilioinguinal neurectomy (Group A) or preservation of the ilioinguinal nerve (Group B). All procedures were conducted by hernia repair specialists under either local or general anaesthesia.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Male patients aged 18-60 years.
2. Patients with unilateral inguinal hernias, either direct or indirect.
3. Elective surgery candidates with a good performance status.
4. Patients with uncomplicated unilateral hernias.
5. Patients scheduled for elective hernia repair.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Male patients with bilateral inguinal hernias.
2. Patients under 18 years of age.
3. Female patients with inguinal hernias.
4. Male patients with complicated inguinal hernias, such as obstructed or strangulated hernias, requiring emergency treatment.
5. Patients with recurrent hernias.
6. Individuals with a history of peripheral neuropathy.
7. Those with impaired cognitive function.
8. Patients with poor performance status.

The primary outcome was the incidence of groin pain at six months post-operation. Secondary outcomes included groin numbness, and postoperative sensory changes in the groin area. Follow-up and assessments were conducted at one and six months after surgery. Eligible patients were those older than 18 with primary unilateral uncomplicated inguinal hernias presenting for surgery at Mahatma Gandhi Hospital, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College. After receiving ethical approval

Results:

This prospective study involved 60 patients with uncomplicated inguinal hernia who underwent

Lichtenstein mesh hernioplasty. The study was divided into two groups: 30 patients with preservation of the ilioinguinal nerve (Group A) and 30 patients with elective division of the nerve (Group B).

In Group A, the average age of patients was 39.6 years, whereas in Group B it was 41.2 years. The condition was most prevalent after the 3rd decade of life, with a predominance of males. Group A consisted entirely of males, while Group B included 96.7% males and 3.3% females. In Group A, 46.7% of patients were heavy workers, 28.3% were light workers, and 25% were moderate workers. Group B had 50% heavy workers, 26.6% light workers, and 23.4% moderate workers.

Patients primarily presented with swelling (approximately 70%), while about 30% experienced both swelling and pain. In Group A, 53.3% of patients had symptoms for less than 6 months, 26.7% had symptoms for 6-12 months, and 20% had symptoms lasting more than 1 year. In Group B, 60% had symptoms for less than 6 months, 30% for 6-12 months, and 10% for more than 1 year. The most common hernia type was right-sided, followed by left-sided, with only a few cases being bilateral.

In terms of hospitalization, Group A had 43.3% of patients staying 3-4 days, 36.7% staying 1-2 days, and 20% staying 5 days or more. Group B had 60% of patients hospitalized for 1-2 days, 30% for 3-4 days, and 10% for 5 days or more. Predisposing factors in Group A included smoking (26.6%), constipation (16.7%), and chronic cough (6.7%). For Group B, the main factors were smoking (23.3%), constipation (20%), and chronic cough (3.3%). Postoperative complications in Group A included urinary retention in 13.3% of patients, testicular edema in 10%, and wound infection in 3.3%. In Group B, 20% of patients experienced urinary retention, and 6.6% had testicular edema.

Table 1:

Post-operative pain	Group A (n=30)	Group B (n=30)	P value
	N (%)	N (%)	
POD-1	28 (93.33)	21 (70)	> 0.05
POD-3	26 (86.67)	18 (60)	<001
POD-7	19 (63.33)	13 (43.33)	0.041
1 month	17 (56.67)	11 (36.67)	0.03
3 months	12 (40)	3 (10)	0.0001
6 months	9 (30)	3 (10)	0.034
1 Year	7 (23.33)	2 (6.67)	0.05

Table 2:

Inc of post-operative hypothesis	Group-A (n=30)		Group-B (n=30)		P value
	No.	%	No.	%	
Day 1	19	63.33	19	63.33	1.0
Day 3	16	53.33	18	60	0.93
Day 7	12	40	15	50	0.71

1 month	9	30	10	33.33	0.8
3 months	7	23.33	6	20	0.8
6 months	5	16.67	5	16.67	1.0
1 year	3	10	5	16.67	0.75

Table 3:

Inc of post-operative numbness	Group-A (n=30)		Group-B (n=30)		P value
	No.	%	No.	%	
Day 1	7	23.33	4	13.33	0.54
Day 3	7	23.33	7	23.33	1.0
Day 7	6	20	7	23.33	0.8
1 month	6	20	7	23.33	0.8
3 months	6	20	6	20	1.0
6 months	5	16.67	5	16.67	1.0
1 year	3	11.11	5	16.67	0.8

Discussion

Chronic groin pain is a frequent and challenging complication following open mesh hernia repair. Some research suggests that routine excision of the ilioinguinal nerve may help reduce the occurrence of persistent groin pain, though this approach remains debated. This study aimed to compare the outcomes of preserving versus selectively dividing the ilioinguinal nerve on postoperative pain, hypoesthesia, and numbness after Lichtenstein tension-free inguinal hernia repair. Conducted at the Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Hospital, Jaipur, the study involved 50 patients divided into two groups: Group A (25 patients) and Group B (25 patients), with follow-up extending up to one year post-surgery.

Results showed that on the first postoperative day (POD-1), 93.3% of patients in Group A reported pain, compared to 70% in Group B. By one year, 23.3% of Group A patients still experienced mild pain, while only 6.67% of Group B did. The difference in pain levels became statistically significant after the third postoperative day. Comparative studies by Kumar et al. and Amuthan et al. reported varying rates of postoperative neuralgia between the two groups, with significant differences observed at different follow-up points. Regarding hypoesthesia, no significant differences were found between Group A (63.3% on POD-1 to 10% at one year) and Group B (63.3% on POD-1 to 16.6% at one year). These results align with studies by Picchio et al., Kumar et al., and Amutha et al., though statistical significance varied. Similarly, numbness rates showed no significant differences between Group A (23.3% on POD-1 to 11.1% at one year) and Group B (13.3% on POD-1 to 16.6% at one year), consistent with findings from Picchio et al., Kumar et al., and Amutha et al.

To summarize, electively dividing the ilioinguinal nerve appears to effectively alleviate chronic postoperative groin pain while causing minimal sensory disturbances. Despite the limitations of

sample size and follow-up duration, ilioinguinal neurectomy should be considered a standard practice in open mesh hernia repairs.

Conclusion

This prospective randomized trial indicates that prophylactic ilioinguinal nerve excision during Lichtenstein inguinal hernia repair significantly reduces the incidence of chronic exertional groin pain postoperatively.

Moreover, the procedure does not lead to additional morbidities, such as increased sensory disturbances or a decline in quality of life. Therefore, ilioinguinal neurectomy is recommended as a routine component of open mesh hernia repair procedures.

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